

Exploring the metal-poor inner Milky Way with the *Pristine* survey

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Stars are excellent messengers from the distant past, since the composition of their atmospheres resembles that of the gas out of which they were born. Ancient stars which formed very early in the Universe were born with few metals, and today they can be recognised as very low-metallicity stars. These are typically searched for and found in the most metal-poor component of the Milky Way, the Galactic halo, and in the satellite dwarf galaxies. However, we also expect them to be present in the very inner regions of our Galaxy, and those are in fact likely among the oldest stars in the Milky Way. The inner Galaxy has largely been avoided in the search for metal-poor stars due to challenges with dust extinction, crowding, and the presence of an overwhelming majority of more metal-rich stars. Very efficient pre-selection methods are necessary to uncover a large number of metal-poor stars in the bulge region, allowing us to study the properties of the metal-poor inner Galaxy.

The Pristine Inner Galaxy Survey (PIGS)

One efficient method of identifying metal-poor stars is using metallicity-sensitive narrow-band photometry, for example the CFHT/MegaCam *CaHK* photometry employed by the *Pristine* survey [1]. The *Pristine* survey has been immensely successful at uncovering metal-poor stars in the halo and dwarf galaxies, and encouraged by this success we started the *Pristine* Inner Galaxy Survey (PIGS) towards the Galactic bulge. The goals of PIGS are to find many of the oldest, metal-poor stars hiding in the inner Galaxy, and to study the properties of the metal-poor tail of the bulge and inner halo.

We spectroscopically followed up metal-poor candidates selected with *CaHK* and broad-band photometry using AAOmega+2dF on the Anglo-Australian Telescope (AAT), and derived stellar parameters including metallicities for this low/intermediate-resolution AAT sample. Figure 1 presents the metallicity distribution of the spectroscopic PIGS sample [2], compared to more “typical” bulge surveys (APOGEE [3] and ARGOS [4]) and compared to the pioneer large survey of metal-poor inner Galaxy stars EMBLA [5]. It shows that the PIGS strategy has been extremely successful at targeting the metal-poor tail of the inner Galaxy, with the largest number ($N = 1900$) of very metal-poor (VMP, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$) stars to date. The unique PIGS sample can be used to study many scientific questions, two of which will be touched upon in these proceedings: how do the metal-poor inner Galaxy stars move compared to their more metal-rich counter parts, and what do the chemically peculiar carbon-enhanced metal-poor stars tell us about differences between the inner Galaxy and rest of the halo?

Figure 1: Top: relative metallicity distribution of PIGS compared to “typical” bulge surveys APOGEE [3] and ARGOS [4], and the dedicated metal-poor bulge survey EMBLA [5]. Bottom: absolute number of VMP stars in each of these surveys. Figure adapted from [2] and updated with additional data.

PIGS kinematics

The “normal”, more metal-rich stars in the Galactic bulge have a boxy/peanut-shaped distribution and show signatures of solid-body rotation. This has been interpreted as the result of bulge formation through instabilities in the early Galactic disk, with little room for a classical, pressure-supported component [e.g., 6, 7]. There have been hints in recent years that for low-metallicity stars the rotation is slower or barely present at all [7, 8], pointing to a pressure-supported origin – a classical bulge and/or the extension of the halo. These studies were typically limited by small sample sizes.

With PIGS we have the perfect sample to study the behaviour of the (very) metal-poor tail of the inner Galaxy as function of metallicity. Figure 2 shows the rotation curve of the stars in PIGS, separated in four different metallicity bins [9]. For the first time, we clearly see a decrease in the strength of rotation with decreasing metallicity, until practically no rotational signature is left for the VMP stars. We also found that the velocity dispersion increases with decreasing metallicity [9]. These observations may point to a transition between the more metal-rich boxy bulge and the more metal-poor inner halo, but can also be related to other processes in the early inner Galaxy such as the exact process of how the boxy bulge formed and the number of metal-poor stars present in the early disk, and/or the dynamical influence of the bar on the halo.

Figure 2: Rotation curve of PIGS stars as a function of metallicity, with the most metal-rich bin on the top left and the most metal-poor bin on the bottom right. Dashed and dotted lines are boxy bulge models from [6]. Based on a figure from [9] and updated with additional data.

PIGS CEMP stars

Besides comparing the dynamics of metal-rich and metal-poor inner Galaxy stars, we can use PIGS to compare the chemistry of VMP inner Galaxy stars to that of “typical” VMP halo stars. Of particular interest are the carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars – it has been recognised that many of the VMP stars in the halo have a large over-abundance in carbon, and that the relative fraction of CEMP stars increases with decreasing metallicity [e.g. 10, 11]. CEMP stars can form through interaction with a binary companion (mainly CEMP-s stars), or they could be *born* carbon-rich (mainly CEMP-no stars). The CEMP-no stars are extremely useful for learning about the early chemical enrichment in the Milky Way. Previously, only a handful of CEMP stars were known in the inner Galaxy, potentially with a much lower fraction compared to the halo.

The large sample size of PIGS, combined with the advantage that our analysis method can provide carbon abundance estimates from the AAT spectra, allows us to further investigate the inner Galaxy CEMP population. We identified 94 new CEMP stars in PIGS, increasing the known number towards the bulge by a factor of ten [12]. It is curious that the *fraction* of CEMP stars in PIGS is much lower than in the literature for the halo, as shown in Figure 3. The fraction is most discrepant for the more

metal-rich stars, and largely consistent for the extremely metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3.0$) stars. We investigated and discarded the possibility that this could be solely due to photometric selection effects, although they may play a role. Instead, the low CEMP fraction may point to a faster early chemical evolution in the (larger) building blocks that made the metal-poor inner Galaxy compared to the rest of the halo, resulting in fewer CEMP-no stars, and/or to a lower binary fraction in the inner Galaxy resulting in fewer CEMP-s stars.

Figure 3: The fraction of CEMP stars in PIGS (black) compared to the literature halo CEMP fraction from [11] (orange). Based on a figure from [12].

Summary and outlook

With PIGS, we have successfully built a large sample of (very) metal-poor stars in the inner Galaxy. We studied the kinematics of the metal-poor inner Galaxy and investigated the occurrence of the chemically peculiar CEMP stars, leading to new insights into the ancient history of the central Milky Way. Further work will include a more extensive orbital analysis of the PIGS sample, high-resolution spectroscopic follow-up for detailed chemical abundances, and preparation for future large spectroscopic surveys such as 4MOST [13].

References

- [1] Starkenburg, E., et al. 2017, MNRAS, 471, 2587
- [2] Arentsen, A., et al. 2020, MNRAS, 496, 4964
- [3] SDSS-IV Collaboration 2020, ApJS, 249, 3
- [4] Ness, M., et al. 2013a, MNRAS, 430, 836
- [5] Howes, L. M., et al. 2016, MNRAS, 460, 884
- [6] Shen, J., et al. 2010, ApJ, 720, L72
- [7] Ness, M., et al. 2013b, MNRAS, 432, 2092
- [8] Kunder, A., et al. 2016, ApJ, 821, L25
- [9] Arentsen, A., et al. 2020, MNRAS, 491L, 11
- [10] Beers, T. C. & Christlieb N. 2005, ARA&A, 43, 531
- [11] Placco, V. M., et al. 2014, ApJ, 797, 21
- [12] Arentsen, A., et al. 2021, MNRAS, 505, 1239
- [13] de Jong, R. S., et al. 2019, The Messenger, 175, 3

Short CV

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